

Basal application of fertilizer reduces golden apple snail population

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Commercial molluscicides are widely used by rice farmers to control the golden apple snail (GAS) *Pomacea canaliculata* (Lamarck). Chemical control is an additional expense and a burden to rice farmers. In addition, misuse of these synthetic pesticides not only pollutes the environment but also poses hazards to applicators, farm workers, work animals, and other nontarget organisms such as fish, frogs, and beneficial arthropods.

In the experimental fields of PhilRice in Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, we observed dead GAS after transplanting in fields with no pesticide. Farm interviews did not provide conclusive answers on whether farm implements (i.e., hand tractor) caused the death of GAS. Neighboring farmers claimed that, when applied before planting (soil incorporation), inorganic fertilizers reduced the GAS population and minimized damage, such as missing hills. We searched various literature databases and contacted snail researchers in the country and abroad but

did not find published or unpublished information on the effects of inorganic fertilizers on snails.

Thus, a series of trials on the effect of different inorganic fertilizers were conducted at PhilRice. A basal rate recommendation of complete fertilizer (14-14-14), urea (40-0-0), and complete fertilizer + urea was used in trial 1 during the 1999 wet season (WS). Handpicking, molluscicide, and no fertilizer served as the untreated control. In trials 2 and 3, during the 2000 dry season (DS) and WS, respectively, the recommended rate of ammonium phosphate (16-20-0) + urea was added as a treatment in place of handpicking. In trial 4, single-element fertilizers (urea, solophos, muriate of potash, and commercial organic fertilizer) were compared with molluscicide (niclosamide 250 EC) to pinpoint the fertilizer element that caused GAS mortality.

Each microplot measured 4 m², replicated four times. Treatments were

arranged in a randomized complete block design in all trials. IR64 seedlings (18-d-old) were transplanted at one seedling hill⁻¹, spaced 20 × 20 cm. Levees of 30 × 30 cm were constructed to separate microplots and to avoid GAS transfer and fertilizer seepage. Fertilizer treatments were applied before final leveling and transplanting was done immediately after leveling. Freshly collected adult GAS were sorted according to size and acclimatized for 48 h. Shell length measured 20–35 mm. Twelve GAS of assorted sizes (4 each of small, medium, and large, with 1 female:1 male) were randomly distributed in each microplot. After several days, the number of dead GAS was counted. Dead GAS had the following characteristics: they floated on the water surface, they had partially opened opercula, they did not respond to mechanical stimuli, and they emitted an unpleasant odor.

Minimal damage (missing hills) was observed on different fertilizer treatments during the first 2 d (Tables 1 and 2). GAS

Table 1. Missing hills (%) caused by GAS in various basal fertilizer treatments, PhilRice, 1999 WS and 2000 DS and WS. ^a

Treatment	Rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	1999 WS			2000 DS		2000 WS				
		1 DAT	3 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	3 DAT	1 DAT	2 DAT	3 DAT	4 DAT	7 DAT
14-14-14 (complete fertilizer)	40-40-40	5.5 ab	16.2 ab	32.8 a	5.5 c	17.7 b	11.2 ab	30.2 bc	31.7 b	54.0 b	58.0 bc
Urea	40-0-0	8.7 ab	22.0 ab	40.0 a	17.2 bc	69.2 a	18.7 a	43.2 b	44.2 b	64.0 ab	73.5 ab
14-14-14 + urea (complete fertilizer + urea)	60-40-40	6.0 b	12.2 b	32.7 a	3.7 c	25.7 b	3.5 b	20.0 cb	23.0 bc	44.7 b	53.2 cb
16-20-0 + urea (ammonium phosphate + urea)	60-40-0	–	–	–	23.5 ab	84.0 a	7.0 ab	28.0 bcd	30.0 b	42.2 b	44.0 c
Molluscicide (niclosamide 250 EC)	1.0 L ha ⁻¹	0.3 c	1.5 c	7.3 b	2.0 c	7.2 c	1.5 b	6.7 d	6.7 c	6.7 c	7.7 d
Untreated (no fertilizer, no molluscicide)	–	10.5 a	19.7 ab	33.5 a	35.0 a	83.2 a	12.0 ab	69.2 a	72.5 a	84.5 a	92.0 a

^aValues followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. – = no data available, DAT = days after treatment, WS = wet season, DS = dry season. Values were arcsine-square root-transformed before analysis. Untransformed values are reported.

became inactive and immobile in plots treated with inorganic fertilizer and may have died because of visibly intensified mucus secretion. The major organ in GAS responsible for mucus production and release is the skin, in which various types of mucus cells can be found. As the GAS became immobilized, they may have additionally been exposed to unfavorable conditions. Desiccation by exposure to sunlight may have accelerated the lethal effects of inorganic fertilizers, but this appeared to be a side effect rather than a direct cause of death. Dead GAS in

fertilizer-treated plots had opened opercula but in niclosamide-treated plots the opercula were closed. GAS mortality (48.0–95.9%) was highest on molluscicide-treated microplots (Table 3). Fertilizer treatment reduced the GAS population to a maximum of 54.1% 7 d after treatment using a basal recommendation of 60-40-40 kg ha⁻¹ of complete fertilizer combined with urea. However, in the single-element and commercial organic fertilizer trial, no GAS mortality was observed (Table 2). Therefore, we conclude that the

combination of three elements (N, P, and K) caused the death of GAS.

Basal application of complete fertilizer (soil incorporation) in combination with urea at the recommended rate reduced the GAS population by 54%, thus preventing GAS damage to the crop during the first 2 d. This reduces the need to apply molluscicide. In addition, handpicking of snails becomes more efficient as the rice field water clears after application of inorganic fertilizers.

Table 2. Effect of single-element fertilizer on GAS mortality (%) and missing hills (%), PhilRice, 2000 WS.^a

Treatment	Rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	6 h		1 DAT		3 DAT		5 DAT		7 DAT	
		GAS mortality	MH	GAS mortality	MH	GAS mortality	MH	GAS mortality	MH	GAS mortality	MH
Urea	40-0-0	0.0 b	1.2 a ^a	0.0 b	3.0 dc	0.0 b	11.5 c	0.0 b	17.2 d	0.0 b	21.7 d
Solophos (0-8-10)	0-40-0	2.0 b	2.2 a	2.0 b	7.7 b	2.0 b	15.5 c	2.0 b	21.2 cd	2.0 b	28.0 cd
Muriate of potash (0-18-0)	0-0-40	0.0 b	1.2 a	0.0 b	8.2 ab	0.0 b	24.0 b	0.0 b	31.2 b	0.0 b	37.0 b
Organic fertilizer (commercial organic fertilizer)	8 bags ha ⁻¹	0.0 b	2.7 a	0.0 b	12.2 a	0.0 b	36.0 a	0.0 b	51.2 a	0.0 b	60.0 a
Molluscicide (niclosamide 250 EC)	1.0 L ha ⁻¹	31.2 a	1.0 a	93.7 a	1.2 d	93.7 a	1.2 d	93.7 a	1.2 e	93.7 a	1.2 e
Untreated (no fertilizer, no molluscicide)	–	0.0 b	1.5 a	0.0 b	6.0 c	0.0 b	13.7 c	0.0 b	25.2 bc	0.0 b	32.0 bcd

^aValues followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. – = no data available, MH = missing hills, DAT = days after treatment, WS = wet season, DS = dry season. Values were arcsine-square root-transformed before analysis. Untransformed values are reported.

Table 3. GAS mortality (%) as affected by basal application of fertilizers, PhilRice, 1999 WS and 2000 DS and WS.^a

Treatment	Rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	1999 WS			2000 DS		2000 WS				
		1 DAT	3 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	3 DAT	1 DAT	2 DAT	3 DAT	4 DAT	7 DAT
14-14-14 (complete fertilizer)	40-40-40	18.7 c	18.7 c	23.0 bc	12.5 b	20.8 b	37.3 b	37.3 b	41.5 bc	41.5 bc	43.5 bc
Urea	40-0-0	2.1 b	2.1 b	6.2 b	2.0 b	8.3 b	25.0 b	25.0 b	27.0 b	27.0 b	33.3 b
14-14-14 + urea (complete fertilizer + urea)	60-40-40	25.0 c	25.0 c	37.0 c	12.5 b	22.9 b	33.3 b	33.3 b	52.0 bc	52.0 bc	54.1 bc
16-20-0 + urea (ammonium phosphate + urea)	60-40-0	–	–	–	4.1 b	8.3 b	18.8 b	18.8 b	27.2 bc	29.3 b	31.3 b
Molluscicide (niclosamide 250 EC)	1.0 L ha ⁻¹	48.0 d	75.0 d	77.1 d	83.3 c	95.9 c	70.8 c	70.8 c	75.0 c	75.0 c	75.0 c
Untreated (no fertilizer, no molluscicide)	–	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a

^aValues followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. – = no data available, DAT = days after treatment, WS = wet season, DS = dry season. Values were arcsine-square root-transformed before analysis. Untransformed values are reported.